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MECHANISMS OF CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE CYBERSECURITY MANAGEMENT AT THE STATE LEVEL

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Abstract. The authors form mechanisms of critical infrastructure cybersecurity management at the state level on the basis of analysis and synthesis of cyber threats for critical infrastructure. The authors show that the type of cyber security management strategy of the specified infrastructure is determined not by one or more of these parameters, but by the role of the department officially responsible for the national cyber security of this infrastructure in the process of implementing measures to protect critical resources from cyber-attacks. Without the involvement of representatives of each specific area of critical infrastructure, the development of measures to protect such infrastructure can begin to focus on false security goals and ignore practical experience, setting requirements that are difficult to meet due to existing constraints. To solve this issue, some countries are diversifying the methods of protecting critical infrastructure, involving stakeholders of such infrastructure in the process of protecting it.

Keywords: critical infrastructure, cybersecurity management, state, mechanisms.

Introduction

The specifics of various areas classified as critical infrastructure require special attention to ensure security. For each specific area, the protection measures used must meet security goals, which often conflict with the principles of confidentiality or availability of information resources, etc.

In addition, often the set of protection measures is adjusted according to the limitations of physical resources and processes, or the requirements of functional security. In many cases, this requires close cooperation between regulatory agencies, as well as specialists responsible for protection measures and representatives of specific enterprises.

The problem of organizing such interaction is especially relevant for private enterprises. Partnership programs of the public and private sectors in the field under consideration are usually aimed at solving this problem.

The presence of critical infrastructure cybersecurity management mechanisms at the state level meets the current security needs of each critical infrastructure industry, taking into account its specific limitations, and contributes to the safe development of all industries in the long term. Therefore, it is interesting to trace and compare indicators of maturity of cyber security management at the state level.

Literature review

The authors (Kaliakin, S. V., Onishchenko, Y. M. and Nosov, V. V., 2023) claim that The experience of other countries concerning protecting critical municipal infrastructure from cyber threats is investigated, analyzed and summarized. The influence of the latest information technologies (such as the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence, blockchain) on the development of municipal infrastructure, the use of these technologies to protect critical infrastructure from cyber-attacks, their advantages and disadvantages compared to classical security technologies are

considered. Special attention is paid to the problems of safe automation of modern city management processes, such as automation of traffic control systems, environmental monitoring systems, financial systems, power grids, water and gas supply systems, communication systems, sewage treatment plant management systems. The features of cyber-attacks and the use of methods of protection of critical infrastructure in the context of hybrid war are investigated.

The authors of the work (Dimitra Markopoulou & Vagelis Papakonstantinou, 2021) argue that the concept of "Critical Infrastructure" is constantly evolving to reflect current problems and respond to new challenges, especially in terms of cyber security and sustainability. Therefore, the protection of critical infrastructure from numerous threats has become a high priority at the national and European levels. In order to ensure the protection of critical infrastructure, the analysis of this work was initially aimed at finding out the differences between critical infrastructures and critical information infrastructures, which are often confused, and pointing out possible shortcomings in the applicable regulatory protection mode. Finally, the health sector was chosen as a specific case to demonstrate in this example how critical infrastructure protection is implemented.

The author of the work (Duncad Card, 2023) shows the fact that North America's critical infrastructure has been the subject of cyberattacks for years. So, in March 2017, a cyber-attack caused periodic "blind spots" for power grid operators in the Western United States for about 10 dangerous hours. In May this year, in many states in the southeastern United States, there was a panic about gas pumps, which was associated with a cyber-attack on a large US pipeline that disrupted the supply of fuel to the east coast of the United States.

The article (Viganò, E., Loi, M. & Yaghmaei, E., 2020) contains a political and philosophical analysis of the values that are key in ensuring of the cybersecurity of critical infrastructures. The work provides an overview of the limits of cybersecurity

in national security, with a focus on the ethics of tracking the protection of critical infrastructures and the use of artificial intelligence. Bibliographic literature analysis applies until 2016 to identify and discuss conflicts of cybersecurity value and ethical issues in national security. This is integrated with an analysis of the latest literature on cyber threats for national infrastructure and the role of artificial intelligence.

Accordingly, the purpose of the work is to form mechanisms of critical infrastructure cybersecurity management at the state level on the basis of analysis and synthesis of cyber threats for critical infrastructure.

Methodology

Analysis and synthesis of cyber threats for critical infrastructure is carried out in the work. In particular, analysis is a method of research, consisting in the imaginary dismemberment of a whole phenomenon into components -more simple, highlighting individual sides, properties, links. Synthesis is a method of research, consisting in the imaginary connection of individual sides, properties, connections of the phenomenon of complex and comprehension of the whole in its unity.

Main part

It is advisable to analyze the cyber security profile of 196 countries constructed by the International Telecommunication Union. For an approximate assessment of the maturity of the cyber security management mechanisms concerning critical infrastructure, the following measures implemented at the state level were considered:

- there is an officially adopted strategy or policy for cyber security of critical infrastructure;
- an official department responsible for ensuring such security is created;
- an official agency responsible for reporting and processing cyber security incidents in critical infrastructure is created;

- there is an officially approved program of interdepartmental cooperation in the given field;
- there is an officially approved public-private cooperation program in the given field (Figure 1).

The combination of these parameters determines the maturity level of critical infrastructure cyber security management.

Nevertheless, the type of cyber security management strategy of the specified infrastructure is determined not by one or more of these parameters, but by the role of the department officially responsible for the national cyber security of this infrastructure in the process of implementing measures to protect critical resources from cyber-attacks.

Figure 1. International Telecommunication Union Cyber Wellbeing Profile for 196 countries

Source: compiled on the basis of [7]

As a rule, the competence of the specified department includes the following duties:

- managing activities to ensure cyber security of critical infrastructure at the state level;
- ensuring interaction between departments whose interests are affected by such cyber security issues;
- adopting by-laws regulating measures of cyber protection of critical infrastructure;
- determining identification criteria and identifying vital systems;
- determining the required set of technical protection measures for each component of the critical infrastructure;
- describing and, if possible, supporting the cybersecurity processes of the critical infrastructure;
- assessing the cyber security of systems and certify cyber protection products according to established criteria;
- promotion of cooperation between the public and private sectors in the given field.

The analysis of the practice of cyber security management of critical infrastructure from the point of view of the interaction between the state and the private sector allowed us to identify three main types of strategies for this management, which are discussed below. As a rule, the choice of a specific strategy is determined by the joint development of regulatory and executive bodies in the field of national security, cyber security, and the security of individual components of critical infrastructure.

Timely attention to the specifics of the strategy and its inherent shortcomings can ensure effective management of critical infrastructure security. The following

comparison of strategy types is aimed at identifying these shortcomings and how to eliminate them.

In this context, first of all, it is necessary to consider a centralized approach to the management of this activity. There is a main administration – a state body or department that is solely responsible for ensuring the cyber security of critical infrastructure. The rest of the institutions may advise this department or participate in activities related to the provision of such cyber security, but do not have a decisive influence on the regulation of this activity. This approach is implemented, for example, in Germany, Italy, the Czech Republic and Estonia.

Security measures are usually well documented and generally apply to all areas of management responsibility, except where they are expressly provided for by law.

The main administration deals with departments of cyber security of critical infrastructure at the state level and, as a rule, is also responsible for its protection against cyber-attacks. To do this, it formulates directives and recommendations at the sub-legal level, establishes certification requirements, develops relevant guidance documents and supports long-term state programs (such as the UP Kritis program in Germany) [2; 4; 6].

This centralized approach is enshrined in Germany's Cyber Security Strategy: "The protection of the most important information infrastructures is a cyber security priority. They are a central component of almost all critical infrastructures and are becoming increasingly important. The public and the private sector must create an improved strategic and organizational framework for closer coordination based on an intensive exchange of information". Germany's Federal Office for Information Security is the main body responsible for the protection of critical information infrastructures at the federal level. Its activities are controlled by the Federal Ministry of the Interior. As the protection of critical infrastructure is seen as a network task involving different authorities at different levels, all relevant cyber security programs

and initiatives are coordinated by the German Federal Office for Information Security.

In the Czech Republic, the main body is the Office of National Security, which is responsible for the cyber security of critical infrastructure, the protection of classified information, the management of security clearances and the management of cryptographic protection. The actual protection of this infrastructure is carried out by the National Cyber Security Center, which is a structural part of the same administration. In the event of a significant cyber security incident, the Office acts as the lead authority coordinating the work of other agencies to resolve the incident (including various public and private agencies). At the same time, the activities of various entities depend on the decisions of the National Security Office in the event of a declaration of a state of emergency and may be carried out in the process of eliminating a cyber security threat or its consequences. The management supports operators of critical infrastructure during an emergency and, if necessary, provides investigation of incidents [2; 4; 6].

The active cooperation of the regulator and the national body to ensure the cyber security of such an infrastructure is an indicator of the openness of the regulator, its awareness of short-term industry needs in security measures and readiness to build relations with the private sector.

Overall, an analysis of the International Telecommunication Union's Cyber Wellbeing Profiles found that of the 129 countries that have an official body responsible for cybersecurity, 90 have an official department for critical infrastructure cybersecurity. In 11 of these 90 countries, it is the above-mentioned authorized body (this is a pretty good indicator of the distribution of duties in most countries). If we consider only those countries that have an officially adopted strategy or policy for the cybersecurity of critical infrastructure, then there are only 64 of the 196 countries for which cyber-wellness profiles have been compiled remain. Among these 64 ones,

only 7 countries do not distinguish between a specialized and a main body responsible for cyber security issues of such infrastructure.

So, 64 states out of 196 ones demonstrate a mature approach to managing cyber security of critical infrastructure (Figure 2).

Fig. 2.2. Distribution of indicators of maturity of cyber security management of critical infrastructure in the countries of the world

Source: compiled on the basis of [7]

Regardless of the organizational form of the main management, this strategy often faces problems of building relations with the private sector, which is most often explained by the uniform requirements for the implementation of cyber security procedures and measures, regardless of the typical features of the specific field of critical infrastructure. Those in the infrastructure field may doubt that cybersecurity professionals are competent enough in their field to use any of the mechanisms, or fear that they may not see the connection between cyberattacks and possible physical

damage. Owners of private facilities classified as critical infrastructure for cyber security may be reluctant to share information about cyber security breaches [3; 5; 8].

Without the involvement of representatives of each specific area of critical infrastructure, the development of measures to protect such infrastructure can begin to focus on false security goals and ignore practical experience, setting requirements that are difficult to meet due to existing constraints. To solve this issue, some countries are diversifying the methods of protecting critical infrastructure, involving stakeholders of such infrastructure in the process of protecting it.

For example, the German regulator Federal Office for Information Security implements the previously mentioned UP Kritis program. The specified UP Kritis program also operates with concepts that go beyond the scope of information technologies to maintain the availability and strengthen the reliability of critical infrastructure. To ensure comprehensive protection of such infrastructure, measures for physical protection and information technology security should be jointly developed and implemented. Cooperation between industry and the state is successfully implemented within UP Kritis. Organizations participating in the program cooperate on the principle of mutual trust. They exchange ideas and experiences and learn from each other how to protect this infrastructure, act together and thereby find the best solutions. Within UP Kritis, new concepts are also developed, contacts are established, exercises are carried out, a joint approach to anti-crisis management of information technologies is developed and used [9].

Conclusions

Thus, according to the International Telecommunication Union, 51 of 196 countries have implemented an official program or initiative for interagency cooperation on critical infrastructure cyber security. At the same time, 51 countries have implemented to some extent a public-private information exchange program related to the cyber security of such infrastructure. In both cases, in almost a third of

the countries, these initiatives are supported by special administrations for the protection of this infrastructure.

Discussion

In some states, there is no special regulator in the field of cyber security of critical infrastructure, instead, they have special offices with broad powers to support security in national cyberspace. One example is Latvia. Its national body for the protection of critical infrastructure (Information Technology Security Incident Response Institute of the Republic of Latvia) shares a coordinating role with the State Security Service and the Bureau for the Protection of the Constitution within the Ministry of Defense. These bodies work together to assess and manage ongoing information risks to critical infrastructure. The Bureau for the Protection of the Constitution has the right to inspect personnel involved in ensuring the functioning of critical infrastructure facilities, to request the Institute for Response to Information Technology Security Incidents of the Republic of Latvia to conduct an inspection of infrastructure facilities to determine its vulnerability and related risks and make recommendations to interested parties on the elimination of identified deficiencies, and may also make recommendations to government agencies that control owners of critical infrastructure facilities. The Bureau, together with the Institute for Response to Information Technology Security Incidents of the Republic of Latvia, periodically informs the National Information Technology Security Council about current threats to critical infrastructure.

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